

Analysis of fruit and vegetables supply chains

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Abstract

This article analyzes the existing factors affecting the spoilage of fruits and vegetables in Uzbekistan. The method was Principal Component Analysis. The data was collected through a survey from March to June 2020, a total of 314 participants of the fruit and vegetable supply chain (212 suppliers, 26 intermediaries, 26 cold store owners, and 50 exporters). As a result, it was found that sorting and packaging at high temperature and non-compliance with storage norms were the most deeply influencing factors.

Introduction

Based on the nature, climatic conditions, available manpower resources and geographical location of Uzbekistan, the great potential of the country's economy in the production of high-quality fruits and vegetables should not be doubted by almost anyone. However, existing potential and its realization in life are different concepts. Over the past few years, this field has begun to be given great importance in Uzbekistan. This is evidenced by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 23, 2019 Number PF-5853 "On Approval of the Strategy for the Development of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020–2030", special attention is paid to the development of value chains. Also, on March 15, 2023, the Head of State's Decision on «Measures for the implementation of the project «Development of the creation of the added value chain in the fruit and vegetable industry (phase 2)» with the participation of the Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA) was adopted. According to the decision, loan funds will be allocated to project initiators for the creation of fruit and vegetable production, storage,

packaging, processing, shock freezing, logistics (including the purchase of transport equipment) and other capacities, food industry projects, as well as working capital planned. Because the high costs of cleaning, transporting, storing, processing, packaging and certifying products before delivery to the final consumer reduce profits. Taking into account the specific characteristics of fruit and vegetable products, we aim to take into account the processes in the chain from the stage of its delivery to the consumer. At these stages, the study of the activity of each link of the chain and the identification of existing defects in it, as well as the study of the economic mechanisms of interactions between the links, allow to analyze the current state of the supply chain.

Supplier. Our research on the supply of fruit and vegetable products in Uzbekistan showed that the collection of goods includes several thousand growers. In most cases, the volume of one farmer's product for the domestic market or export is from 1 ton (in the case of small land owners, even less) to 50 tons. 60 percent of fruit and vegetable products are grown mainly by small farms. Harvesting is usually done in the first part of

the day, and this is done by the grower himself or with the help of workers hired by the «middleman». It should be mentioned that in 75-80 percent of cases, sorting of newly collected products is done in the field. There are «receivers» in each district, who usually receive the harvest at a fixed time in the afternoon. Until then, the harvested products are stored in cool, shady places. The received product is distributed to the appropriate addresses depending on the required size, caliber and quality.

Consumer. Selling fruit and vegetable products to domestic markets is both convenient and desirable for the grower. The reason is that the price of the products sold in the first harvest and in the yellow state is high, that is, the grower sells in the market at an agreed price depending on the variety and quality of his product. The second and third harvests are handed over to processing enterprises. Processing plants use both agricultural and industrial resources to create products that are ready for consumption. Enterprises of this type can be based on different ownership, be organized on the basis of family farms, and merge with small factories.

There are also cases where large processing enterprises grow products for themselves. As a rule, the surplus of domestic consumption is sold on world markets, the opposite is observed in our country. It can be observed that the volume of fruit and vegetable production in our country is constantly increasing over the years. In the current period, the problems related to providing the population of the country with fruit and vegetable products according to sustainable and medical standards are not caused by the lack of production volume, but by the lack of rational organization of preparation, storage, processing and sales systems. A large number of losses and a decrease in quality are observed in the links of the fruit and vegetable complex from the field to the consumer. This, in turn, causes an increase in the price of products in the markets and a decrease in the competitiveness of local products.

Losses in fruit and vegetable products can also lead to direct losses in terms of quantity. At this point, it is appropriate to define the concept of post-harvest losses and to touch on some trends observed in the world. According to the definition of the World Food and Agriculture Community (FAO), losses are reductions in both quantity and quality of products at all stages from harvesting from the field to the consumer. In this case, the loss

of quality is understood as the reduction of useful substances in the products or their becoming unfit for consumption. Such a loss is characteristic mainly of developed countries. And the loss of quantity, which means a decrease in the volume of production, is more likely to be contributed by developing countries. In developed countries (middle and high income population) there are cases of throwing away products even if they are suitable for consumption. In developing countries, products are lost at various stages (collection, transportation, sorting, storage, processing, etc.) until they reach the final consumption. Among the agricultural products consumed, fruits and vegetables are among the most perishable products¹.

Storage. According to statistical data, 30 percent of products are lost in the process of harvesting and storage of fruit and vegetable products in our country². One of the main elements of the supply chain of fruit and vegetable products is refrigerated warehouses. Depending on the application, fruits and vegetables play an important role in the quality and continuous supply of products. There are different types of cold storage, including:

1. Cold warehouses intended for distribution (organizes the distribution of the flow of perishable products from main transport to ready networks);
2. Refrigerated warehouses intended for preparation (prepare agricultural products for further transportation);
3. Logistics terminals with refrigeration (perishable products
4. arranging shipment to other regions or countries)
5. Refrigerated warehouses of enterprises (intended for the processing of agricultural products);
6. Refrigerated warehouses for reloading (loading of perishable products from rail transport to road transport)
7. Customs refrigerated warehouses for temporary storage;
8. Customs refrigerated warehouses (intended for temporary storage of goods)
9. Refrigerated warehouses of retail chains

The reasons for the above-normal losses in terms of quality and quantity during storage of fruit and vegetable products are as follows:

1. initial quality for storage of fruits and

¹ Cattaneo, A., Federighi, G., & Vaz, S. (2020). The environmental impact of reducing food loss and waste : A critical assessment. *Food Policy*, August 2019, 101890. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodpol.2020.101890>

² www.agro.uz

vegetables;

2. refrigerating warehouses are located far from the field/garden and their storage costs are high;

3. high quality product packaging prices;

4. non-compliance with storage norms.

Uzbekistan is considered a producing country, and it is appropriate to establish sorting and packaging cold storage facilities. In fact, most of the existing cold rooms are used to store finished products. Also, almost 70 percent of warehouses are located 100-200 km away from the place of production. Based on the results of the research, it should be noted that the location of warehouses close to the cultivation areas has a positive effect on product quality and saves transportation costs. Improper proportioning of existing cold storage facilities limits the rational use of warehouse space and leads to violations of storage norms.

Transportation. Reasons for higher than normal losses in terms of quality and quantity during transportation of fruit and vegetable products are as follows:

1. initial quality for transportation of fruits and vegetables;

2. preparation of fruits and vegetables for transportation;

3. pre-cooling;

4. transport

Fruit and vegetable products are brought both to the domestic market and to the railway station for export using ordinary freight vehicles. In the domestic supply chain, this situation is not a big problem, because it does not take much time for the product to be distributed to the domestic market. In the export process, after temperature treatment, it is delivered to the designated station by railway transport, where it is unloaded according to the demand of stores for temporary storage and collection at the fruit and vegetable base, and then delivered to customers by refrigerated trucks from the fruit and vegetable base.

With this technology of transportation, the possibility of cooling perishable fruit and vegetable products before long-distance transportation is not taken into account, which leads to an increase in cargo damage on the road, as well as contradicts scientific recommendations in the field of refrigerated transport, and only manual labor is used at all stages of loading and unloading operations. leads to an increase in cost³.

³ Juraboev K.A. Improving the transportation of perishable goods by adjusting the logistics chain (on the example of the Republic of Uzbekistan), Diss. 04201352511, 2012

Processing. The sharp increase in the volume of fruit and vegetable products gives impetus to the development of the direct processing sector. 20 million tons of fruits and vegetables are grown in our country per year. But the rate of their industrial processing is 15 percent. By the end of 2019, 60 agricultural products processing projects were launched, but by the end of 2020, 16 processing enterprises were not launched⁴.

Fruit and vegetable processing processes differ depending on the raw materials being processed and the types of products being prepared. Therefore, fruit and vegetable processing processes have their own characteristics, which can be described as follows: Seasonality:

1. return at a certain time of the year;

2. duration of one or several months;

Brevity;

1. inability to stockpile raw materials for a certain period of time;

2. daily purchase of raw materials;

Amplitude;

1. at the beginning and end of the season, the enterprise will not have full capacity due to the decrease in the amount of raw materials;

2. increasing the capacity of the enterprise to the maximum when the ripening of processed raw materials is at a high point.

According to the results of research, this situation causes a number of inconveniences for processing enterprises. That is:

1. failure to operate equipment at the enterprise at full capacity;

2. problems in recruiting temporary workers hired for the enterprise;

3. consumption of excess energy due to the fact that the equipment is not at full efficiency.

Literature review

From foreign scholars on theoretical and methodological issues related to supply chain management by L. Cooper, M. Ellram, R. Bamou, J.F. Shapiro, J. Katalin, Ph. Wieser, Van der Vorst, R. J. Hodges, J. Liu, A, R. Sheoran, Y. K. Sharma, J. Parfitt, W. E. Soto-Silva, D. M. Ahmed Research in Fruit and Vegetable Supply Chain⁵.

From local scientists, Yo.K. Karrieva, G'.M. Kasimov, G'.A. Samatov, Q.A. Dadaboev, M.M. Tairova, E. Kamalova, I.B. Rustamov and issues related to the supply chain of fruit and

⁴ Ministry of Agriculture of Uzbekistan

⁵ Cooper, M. and Ellram, L. «Characteristics of Supply Chain Management and the Implications for Purchasing and Logistics Strategy»

vegetable products N.Kh. Borieva, N.R. Asadullina, H.S. Khushvaktova, F.R. Galimova, O.G. Scientists such as Dilmurodov have considered in research work⁶.

Material and methods

As a logical continuation of the theoretically considered issues, the goal was to determine the problems of these links of the supply chain by means of monographic research and interviews. Based on this goal, from March to June 2020, a total of 314 fruits it was necessary to conduct interviews with participants in the vegetable supply chain (212 suppliers, 26 middlemen, 26 cold store owners, 50 exporters), a questionnaire and 3 relatively large processing enterprises.

The reason is the lack of statistical and other types of data necessary for our research work. The questionnaire was considered important to determine the degree of achievement of the desired goal as a result of the planned program, and the educational and methodological manuals and scientific works of a number of foreign scientists on the procedure for conducting a social questionnaire were used in its development.

It consisted of a total of 40 questions, including general and separate questions directly related to the type of activity for each type of respondents. In this process, directly with the help of the experts of the Department of Working with Farmers of the Executive Committee of the Political Council of the UzLiDeP of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Entrepreneurship and Farming Support Center of Uzbekistan, the Association of Exporters of Uzbekistan, and the USAID organization (USA) «Development of the Value Chain in Uzbekistan» project, an anonymous and voluntary survey of respondents was conducted.

According to the social and demographic data of the survey, the types of activity: growers-52.63, intermediaries-15.79, owners of cold stores-10.53, exporter-21.05 percent; by place of residence: urban-26.1, rural-73.9 percent; by gender: 10.8% female, 89.2% male; according to information: high-64.3, middle-34.7%; by territorial location: Tashkent city-6.1, Karakalpakstan-9.1, Kashkadarya-2.5, Tashkent region-5.7, Surkhandarya-5.7, Andijan-11.5, Samarkand 12.7, Jizzakh-1 ,6, Fergana-15.9, Bukhara-2.2, Navoi-1.3, Namangan-4.8, Khorezm-19.7, Syrdarya-1 percent. According to the type of activity, 52.63 percent were producers, 21.05 percent were

exporters, 15.79 percent were middlemen, and 10.53 percent were owners of cold stores. 89.2% of the respondents are men and 10.8% are women. 73.9 percent live in the countryside, 26.1 percent live in the city. 64.3% of the survey participants have higher education and 34.7% have secondary education (Appendix 8).

Reducing the loss of fruits and vegetables not only increases the volume of products, but also ensures food security, and is considered an important factor in increasing the income of agricultural entrepreneurs. It is very important to maintain the quality of products even after harvesting.

However, due to the lack of necessary knowledge, advanced experience and modern technologies, part of the fruit and vegetable products perishes at various stages of the supply chain. This situation is observed at all stages, starting from the production of products, which is the initial link of the chain, to the delivery to the final consumer. In many developing countries, prevention of post-harvest losses is critical to supply chain actors as a source of income, poverty reduction, food security and job creation.

According to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations, 1/3 of the products grown for human consumption, that is, 1.3 billion tons, lose in a year⁷. According to some estimates, about 30–40 percent of the fruits and vegetables harvested from a farmer's field die or are discarded because they are unfit for consumption. Such a situation leads to a sharp decrease in the income of the participants of the supply chain (Figure 3). Loss and waste of products are two different concepts.

For example, the perishability of products occurs during the stages of growing products and their post-harvest management and processing. Waste is observed at the final stage of consumption, which is the last part of the chain, and directly depends on the attitude of consumers and final buyers to food products.

Post-harvest losses are caused by internal and external factors. External factors are caused by mechanical (physical damage during harvesting, packing, loading, unloading and transportation) and damage by parasitic diseases (fungi, bacteria, insects). Microorganisms quickly affect freshly grown products and multiply rapidly due to moisture in them. However, the pesticides used against them reduce the edibility of the product. Internal factors are caused by physiological disorders.

6 O.G. Dilmurodov, Improvement of the logistics chain of product sales in the fruit and vegetable complex under the conditions of economic liberalization, diss. 2010.

7 <https://www.fao.org/3/cc0639en/online/cc0639en.html> (full digital report)

Variables	Description
X1	Territory - on the scale of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Tashkent city and regions
X2	Place
X3	Age
X4	Gender
X5	Education
X6	Form of ownership
X7	Material equipment in the balance sheet
X8	Availability of an international quality certificate
X9	Product delivery location
X10	Use of refrigerated transport
X11	Type of product
X12	Land area, in hectares
X13	Cost, mln. In sum
X14	Yield, in tons
X15	Amount of product sold, in tons
X16	Product price per 1 kg, thousand sums
X17	Volume of losses, in kg
Factors influencing losses included as variables (growers, brokers, exporters and cold storage owners)	
X18	Sorting and packing operations are carried out In the field at high temperatures
X19	NON-compliance with storage norms
X20	Length of product delivery time
X21	Location of cold stores away from fields/gardens
X22	Other reasons

Table 1. Description of variables for analysis⁸

The product continues to breathe even after it has been dialed and causes heat to dissipate. If no action is taken to stop the cooling and ripening process, quality and flavor are lost and spoilage begins. In addition, losses occur for a number of other reasons.

A decrease in the quantity or quality of products at any stage of the supply chain leads to a decrease in profits. In our opinion, in the process of analyzing the damage caused by the perishability of fruit and vegetable products, it is appropriate to study the indirect effects in addition to the direct damage in terms of quantity and quality. For example, it is necessary to take into account the fact that the energy, land and water resources, manpower, transport and other factors spent

on the production of fruit and vegetable products can be spent on the production of other types of consumer products. It is very difficult to completely prevent losses, but it is possible to reduce its level. For example, the year-round availability of products to consumers ensures that imports are reduced and prices are affordable.

Analysis and results. Supply chain involves a complex process, and only those with a greater number of response options were considered. In this case, the occurrence of losses was 53 percent in delivery, 27 percent in sorting, and 20 percent in storage. The delivery process includes the process of processing the product after it is collected from the field, to the domestic market or to the

⁸ Statistical analysis was performed by the author in Stata 15 software

foreign market. Of course, there are a number of problems in the supply chain of fruits and vegetables in Uzbekistan today, the lack of knowledge and skills of harvesters can cause problems related to losses in the entire chain. For example, 100 people should work to pick, sort, cool and export an average of 20 tons of cargo. If the capacity of the cold store is 1000 tons, it is not difficult to imagine how many people need to work to sort the average 250-300 tons of products placed in it. For the free movement of a large number of workers, the area of the cold room is required to be much larger than the volume of product storage. A lot of it comes down to well-informed staff. The conditions are sufficient to move to the sorting mechanism. The work is definitely not over with improving the qualifications of the workers. Currently, our existing cold storages

allow quantitative analysis of development indicators of losses in the supply chain, without neglecting the factors that influence it, and showing the relationship, taking into account the interaction of each factor.

Stata-15 statistical analysis program was used to determine the correlation between the factors we considered. Because this program can help to simplify the calculation and justify the accuracy in the process of statistical analysis. The classification of variables according to the factors mentioned in the questionnaire is presented in the following table 1.

It can be seen from most studies that relatively simple types of econometric models are usually used. In particular, the regression model (OLS) allows you to consider the effect

Component	Eigenvalue	Difference	Proportion	Cumulative
Component 1	1.55549	0.355753	0.3889	0.3889
Component 2	1.19974	0.094562	0.2999	0.6888
Component 3	1.010518	0.965596	0.2763	0.9651
Component 4	0.139584	0	0.0349	1.0000

Table 2. Location of selected factors in components⁹

are able to fulfill their function only up to 60%. For example, if it is intended to export 10 tons of cargo in 10 days, they can only cool 6 tons during this period. The reason is that many people have built the third type of cold storage used for consumption. As a result, sorting works are carried out in the field itself, even if it

of several independent variables on exactly one dependent variable. In real life, we cannot take only one factor as the main influencer, one factor can affect the third factor through the second factor, it can affect several dependent variables at the same time, or some processes can be affected by several

Figure 1. Graphic display of component values¹⁰

does not meet the standards.

The relationship between the factors affecting the increase in the volume of losses can also be analyzed through a number of econometric models. Econometric models

factors at the same time. In doing so, we need more efficient econometric models for research. In the process of analysis, the use of PCA (Principal Component Analysis) models in

⁹ Statistical analysis was performed by the author in Stata 15 software

¹⁰ Statistical analysis was performed by the author in Stata 15 software

Variables	Component 1	Component 2	Component 3	Component 4
Sorting and packing operations are carried out in the field at high temperatures	-0.7727	-0.0356	-0.0356	0.6234
Non-compliance with storage norms	0.5247	-0.6043	-0.2941	0.5226
Length of delivery time	0.2614	0.7823	-0.3448	0.4480
Location of cold stores away from fields/gardens	0.2436	0.0987	0.8907	0.3709

Table 3. Indicators of selected factors in components (loading)¹¹

determining which factors are most responsible for losses in the supply chain of fruit and vegetable products increases the reliability and accuracy of the analysis results. The reason we chose these models is because they have several advantages over other models. In the framework of our research, we select a number of factors affecting the exact losses, one or two of them explaining the rest as a matrix.

Here, components with values greater than 1 are selected (component), that is, the variation should be greater than 10% as mentioned in the above section. We will need to select components by eigenvalue. Looking at the table, the values of component 1 and component 2 are greater than 1, and the value of component 3 is very close to 1. These can be clearly seen in Figure 3 below.

It can be seen that the model presented 4 components by entering the given 4 variables into a matrix. As a rule, three of them were accepted because the value was correct. Now it is time to determine the weight

Determination of the correlation matrix	
Determinant	0.085
Bartlett test of sphericity	
Chi-square	839.217
Degree of freedom	10
p-value	0.000
Kaise mayer Olkin Measure	0.50

Table 3. Indicators of selected factors in components (loading)

(loading) of each of the selected variables in the composition of the components provided by the model. The weight of the factors in the components should be greater than -0, 30 or 0.30 (Table 2).

Noticed that the weights of the selected factors in the components from the above table, the weights of the variables of high temperature sorting and packaging (-0.77) and non-observance of storage norms (0.52) are in accordance with the requirements. It can be concluded that these 2 variables (high temperature sorting and packing and non-observance of storage norms), i.e. these 2

factors affecting the losses, are the other factors (the length of product delivery time and the location of cold storages far from the field/garden) manifests itself.

From the table above, the correlation coefficient matrix corresponding to the Chi-square statistic has a p-value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05, the predicted level of significance, which indicates that the hypothesis that the correlation matrix of these variables is not significant is rejected. It should be noted that the data is almost 86 times larger than the variables obtained from 344 samples (4), where the actual required sample size should be 4-5 times larger than the variables. Kaiser Mayer Olkin Measure (KMO) interprets the adequacy of selected factors, where the value is 0.50. All this justifies the use of factor analysis for this model.

Conclusion

Taking into account the specific characteristics of fruit and vegetable products, it is appropriate to consider the processes in the chain from the stage of its delivery to the consumer. The value chain developed in the global community was shared with some considerations for its implementation in the conditions of Uzbekistan. In conclusion, we can cite the following:

1. In Uzbekistan, great importance is attached to the processes of growing and exporting fruit and vegetable products, but there are shortcomings in the issues of their delivery, storage, and packaging.

2. In improving the current state of the value chain of fruit and vegetable products, it is appropriate to take into account the mutual integration of growing, processing, exporting participants.

3. The opinions of the participants of the supply chain are important when choosing the factors that affect the quantity and quality of losses in fruit and vegetable products. Based on this, we believe that surveys should be conducted among all the links involved in the fruit and vegetable supply chain, that is, growers, processors, warehouse owners, and exporters.

¹¹ Statistical analysis was performed by the author in Stata 15 software

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